

**FACTORS AFFECTING THE PROCESS OF ENROLLMENT OF LEARNERS'
RECORD IN LEARNER INFORMATION SYSTEM IN PUBLIC
ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE DISTRICT OF TERESA**

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Factors Affecting the Process of Enrollment of Learners' Record in Learner Information System in Public Elementary Schools in the District of Teresa

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in in Learner Information System in Public Elementary Schools in the District of Teresa. The respondents of the study were the 196 teachers or 100 percent population of public elementary schools within the district who handled advisory classes and LIS. A researcher-made questionnaire was used as the main instrument in gathering pertinent data through online google survey on the extent of the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data. Findings of the study revealed that the majority of the respondents are 21 - 30 years old, female, married, Teacher I with bachelor's degree and have been in the teaching industry for 5 years and below. Most of them have attended school level seminars / training courses related to LIS. The respondents agree on the factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data. Likewise, age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS are significant on the perceptions of the respondents on the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to participation in system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the respondents' age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS are not contributory on the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to participation in system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data.

Keywords: *LIS, enrollment, elementary schools*

Introduction

Education is an important tool that is applied in the contemporary world to succeed, as it mitigates the challenges which are faced in life. The knowledge gained through education enables individuals' potential to be optimally utilized owing to training of the human mind. This opens doors of opportunities enables individual to achieve better prospects in career growth.

The ever-changing trend in technology brought the necessity for the automation of everything from paper-and-pen based to absolute computer domination. The overwhelming emergence of computers paved way to easier access of information that leads to increased production, efficiency and reliability.

In this regard, the Department of Education initiated the Learner Information System (LIS), an online facility that provides for the registration of learners enrolled in public schools, with the aim of streamlining the work processes of schools, particularly those done by teachers. Among these tasks are the creation of the master list of students every year that serves as basis for attendance, grades, etc. Since its installation, the LIS has allowed the Department to generate the total public-school enrolment based on the actual registration of learners. It also enabled the establishment of a centralized "Learner Registry" where basic learner information is captured, stored and accessed through a secured facility to enhance tracking and decision-making on learners at various levels of DepEd management.

The LIS is an innovative tool that the Department uses to manage information with the aim of promoting transparency, informed decision making, and empowerment at different levels of the organization. While being a tech-based solution, the LIS involves an inclusive, community-driven process that thrives because of the active engagement and participation of all teachers, principals, planning officers and other DepEd personnel all throughout the Philippines.

This system is envisioned to allow the Department to better track its learners in both formal and non-formal instruction so that more appropriate interventions can be formulated in the provision of quality education for all Filipino learners. As an example, students who transfer from one school to another can be monitored and better assisted by using data from the LIS.

Teachers play a significant role in the process of enrolling and updating learners' record in LIS. At the beginning of the School Year and End of the School Year teachers must ensure that all learners are enrolled in LIS and all learners' profile and status must be updated. The Class Adviser shall be responsible for collecting and updating information on learners in the formal school, ensuring that data captured is supported by appropriate legal documents.

Based on the reports in the LIS and personal observation together with ICT coordinators from different school in the District of Teresa, 196 or 100% of teachers in the public elementary school in the District of Teresa encountered several challenges and problems during enrolling learners in LIS. 20% of total enrollees of their respective sections have data issues and enrollment problems. Some of them find difficulty in enrolling learners who came from other schools especially from private schools. They also experienced problems in

creating new LRN for learners who haven't yet submitted legal documents like certificate of Live birth. They are also confused which buttons to select when they are in the system. This may be the factors on why most of the teachers are having problems dealing with LIS. While there are difficulties encountered at the onset of the implementation, ultimately the intent is to simplify and reduce the work entailed in accomplishing learners related forms by our teachers. In order to assess the technical skills of the teachers, the school conducts school-based In-service Training (INSET) programs.

The researcher being a school ICT and LIS coordinator, conceived this study to assess the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in LIS which served as input in enhancing teachers' knowledge in the implementation and reducing mistakes in LIS program

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the extent of the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System in public elementary schools in the District of Teresa during the School Year 2018-2019. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. position title;
 - 1.5. educational attainment;
 - 1.6. length of service; and
 - 1.7. seminars/ trainings attended in LIS?
2. What is the extent of the factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System as perceived by the respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. system quality;
 - 2.1.1. system operation; and
 - 2.1.2. learner information system quality?
 - 2.2. information quality; and
 - 2.3. availability of learners' data?
3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System as perceived by the respondents with respect to cited aspects in terms of their profile?
4. What training program may be proposed to improve the process of enrolling of learners' record in Learner Information System?

Literature Review

According to O'Brien (2013), there are many kinds of information system in the real world. All of them use hardware, software, network, and people resource to transform data resources into information products. Today's technology is influenced by computer. Everywhere you go and everything you do can be manipulated through computer transaction. Computerization has drastically changed the appearance of today's office but with the computer technology growing rapidly the change continue every day in office around the world. The use of computer technology is continuously evolving because technology doesn't stop unless humankind is satisfied. Computers are very helpful tools nowadays they can make work easier and efficient.

In addition, Osakwe (2011) stated that school records are official documents, books and files containing essential and crucial information of actions and events which are kept and preserved in the school office for utilization and retrieval as needed. Such records are kept by principals, teachers, counselors and administrative staff. The purpose of record keeping for effective school management is to ensure that accurate and proper records are kept of student achievement and growth, school activities and matters that will promote school efficiency and effectiveness.

Visscher (2013) said that School Information Systems is an information system based on one or more computers, consisting of data bank and one or more computer applications which altogether enable the computer-supported storage, manipulation, retrieval, and distribution of data to support school management. He also believes that School Information System can provide administrators and teachers with the information required for informed planning, policymaking, and evaluation. Like Learner Information System, it also provides information to school organizational staff that supports them in their strategic management activities.

The study of Cosidon (2016) on Student Information System for Kalinga State University-Rizal Campus she concluded that automation of existing student information system. The performance of the developed Student Information System is superior, more efficient and effective than the existing student information system of the Kalinga State University Rizal campus. With regards to the quality characteristics that were used to evaluate both the existing and the developed Student Information System, it is also concluded that the developed Student Information System is much better than the existing system. In a nutshell, all the stakeholders, such as the faculty

members, students and the administrators found that the developed Student Information System had met their expectations with regards to the student information system.

Moreso, Tangcangco (2017) discussed that Learning Information Systems enable individualized practice and individualized feedback. They are intended to impact on learning effectiveness by providing structured and detailed formative feedback: directly to the learner, directly to the teacher, to the learner mediated and interpreted by the teacher and lastly to any other stakeholders, e.g. parents, head teacher or principal, advisors and inspectors.

Relatively, Pineda (2017) reported that access to the information of students with accurate data is possible thru the innovation initiated by the Department of Education. The said system is a collaborative work of DepEd and Australian Government Aid or AusAid. The said information system is being used to track students and in making sure that they are qualified for the next grade level. Access for students' data even at great distances is possible. In the future, other data such as form 137 and form 138 will be integrated in the system itself.

In the study of Gaylon (2017) on Information and Communication Technology Competencies among Elementary School Teachers of Taytay II-B and Its Implication to Daily Classroom Instruction revealed that the level of ICT competency, for the technology operation and concepts aspects, the teachers are competent in general, as they are competent in computer in data management. Moderately competency of teachers is revealed also for professional aspects such as in exploring new technologies, research on the use of technology and sharing expertise.

Furthermore, the study of Picadizo (2015) on assessment of proficiency in Information and Communication Technology teachers in Binangonan Elementary School found out that the level of proficiency by the teacher respondents in ICT with respect to computer concept, hardware, word processing, spreadsheet, PowerPoint and networking was verbally interpreted as Proficient. It is recommended that in-service training programs to improve the level of proficiency of teachers in ICT should be conducted. Teachers should be exposed to more instructional technology. Activities to enhance their level of proficiency in Information and Communication Technology.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive design. According to Almeida (2016) the descriptive research presents a picture of the specific details of a situation, social setting or relationship. The major purpose of descriptive research is to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon. It seeks to determine the answer to who, what, where, and how questions.

This research design found applicable to present study since it helped the researcher to categorize, manipulate and summarize the data to obtain the needed answers to research questions concerning the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System in public elementary schools in the District of Teresa.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 100% percent of the teachers' population in public elementary schools in the District of Teresa. This consists of 196 teachers.

These teachers are those handling advisory classes and LIS. They were described in terms of age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service, and seminars/ trainings attended in LIS.

Instrument

The study utilized of a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist through online google form to gather the needed data. The instrument consists of two parts. Part I of the questionnaire-checklist dealt with the personal data of teacher respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service, and seminars/ trainings attended in LIS.

Part II of the questionnaire-checklist dealt with the system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data. Each aspect consists of 10 items, with a total of 30 items.

Procedure

Permission from concerned authorities were secured after the validation of the questionnaire-checklist. After the validation of the instrument, the questionnaire-checklist was administered to the respondents through posting and sharing of links of online google survey. Upon retrieval, the data were generated, downloaded and processed. Statistical tools were applied, analyzed and interpreted. From the data, summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations were formulated.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Position Title, Educational Attainment, Length of Service and Seminars and Trainings Attended in LIS

Table 1. *Profile of the Teacher-Respondents*

Age	Frequency	Percent	Rank
21 - 30 years old	61	31.1	1
31 - 40 years old	53	27.0	2
41 - 50 years old	49	25.0	3
51 years old and above	33	16.8	4
Total	196	100.0	
Sex			
Male	35	17.9	2
Female	161	82.1	1
Total	196	100.0	
Civil Status			
Single	67	34.2	2
Married	115	58.7	1
Widow / Widower	13	6.6	3
Separated	1	.5	4
Total	196	100.0	
Position Title			
Teacher I	150	76.5	1
Teacher II	10	5.1	3.5
Teacher III	21	10.7	2
Master Teacher I	10	5.1	3.5
Master Teacher II	5	2.6	5
Total	196	100.0	
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree	107	54.6	1
With MA Units	39	19.9	3
MA/MAT Graduate	47	24.0	2
With Ed.D. / Ph.D. Units	2	1.0	4
Ed.D. / Ph.D. Graduate	1	0.5	5
Total	196	100.0	
Length of Service			
5 years and below	79	40.3	1
6 - 10 years	42	21.4	2
11 - 15 years	32	16.3	3.5
16 - 20 years	11	5.6	5
21 years and above	32	16.3	3.5
Total	196	100.0	
Seminars and Trainings Attended			
School Level	162	82.7	1
District Level	13	6.6	2
Division Level	12	6.1	3
Regional Level	9	4.6	4
Total	196	100.0	

The percentage distribution of the respondents presented that they belong to middle age group at 58.1% and the least percentage of 16.8 belongs to 51 years old and above. The female sex predominates the male sex at 82.1%. As to their civil status, majority of them at 58.7% are already married and only .5% is separated. Their position title shows that there are 76.5% who are still in Teacher I position and few of them at 7.7% are Master Teacher I and II, respectively. Their educational background shows that many among them are bachelor's degree holder at 54.6% and least percentage of .5 obtained their Ed.D. / Ph.D.

With regard to length of service, the highest percentage of 40.3 are teaching for 5 years and below while the lowest percentage of 5.6 are veteran in the world of teaching since they have been in the service for 16 - 20 years. Majority of the teachers attended seminars and trainings about LIS within the school level at 82.7%, then least percentage of 4.6 are already exposed to regional level.

Extent of the Factors Affecting the Enrollment and Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to System Quality (System Operation and Learner Information System Quality), Information Quality and Availability of Learners' Data

As reflected in the table, factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System as perceived by the respondents with respect to system quality (system operation) indicated that the respondents agree that they have the knowledge to log

in using their username and password which obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.95. It is inferred in the highest mean that teachers are aware in accessing the Learner Information System by logging in using their intended username and password.

Table 2. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Extent of the Factors Affecting the Enrollment and Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to System Quality (System Operation)*

A. System Quality		Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>A.1 System Operation</i>				
<i>I know how to, ...</i>				
1.	connect in Learner Information System.	3.92	Agree	2
2.	log in using my username and password.	3.95	Agree	1
3.	enroll learners using enroll button, during Beginning of the School Year (BOSY).	3.89	Agree	3
4.	search learners record using search button in the absence of learners' legal document.	3.61	Agree	4
5.	create new record and input his/her information if learner is not yet listed in the system.	3.02	Neutral	10
6.	update learners' record using request correction button, if there are inconsistencies in his/ her data.	3.45	Neutral	6
7.	update learners' record using update other data button, if there are any changes in his/her data like residency.	3.44	Neutral	7
8.	update learners' status and input his/ her final grade using status pen at the End of the School Year. (EOSY)	3.54	Agree	5
9.	finalize my class using "finalize button".	3.17	Neutral	9
10.	connect on "my own" internet connection to do the necessary operations and actions mentioned above.	3.31	Neutral	8
Composite Mean		3.53	Agree	

Findings imply that LIS is an innovative tool that the teachers use to manage the information of their learners. Likewise, teachers know how to access the said application, but they are not that aware in creating new account when one of his/her learners are not yet included in LIS. This may be due to the reason that they teachers are not that exposed with the different system operation offered by the LIS. Having the ability to explore the different system operation rendered by the LIS helps them to handle more task.

This is related to the discussion of Shah (2014) which emphasized that computers are seen to have the potential to make a significant contribution to the teaching, learning, and administration in schools. Computer can be considered as another instrument for developing system like enrollment in every school. This can be a great help to teachers and school who are handling many tasks from providing easier and faster access.

Table 3. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Extent of the Factors Affecting the Enrollment and Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to System Quality (Learner Information System Quality)*

A. System Quality		Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>A.2 Learner Information System Quality</i>				
<i>The system, ...</i>				
1.	is easy to use and accessible.	3.58	Agree	5
2.	respond quickly enough.	3.45	Neutral	8
3.	is always up and running.	3.12	Neutral	9
4.	can manage huge number of users at a time.	2.88	Neutral	10
5.	analyze learners' information and refuse to create multiple LRN and duplicate enrollment.	3.48	Neutral	6
6.	special facility (Correction of Learners' data) is effective and useful.	3.89	Agree	3
7.	had improved my communication with other schools.	3.46	Neutral	7
8.	includes almost all the school forms needed by the teachers. (e.g. SF1, SF2. SF3 and SF5)	4.16	Agree	1
9.	have reminders and alerts posted to reduce error.	4.11	Agree	2
10.	Learner Information System is satisfactory.	3.73	Agree	4
Composite Mean		3.59	Agree	

As revealed in the table, the factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System as perceived by the respondents with respect to system quality (learner information system quality) indicated that the respondents agree that the system includes almost all the school forms needed by the teachers. (e.g. SF1, SF2. SF3 and SF5) which obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.16. This means that the LIS includes the generalize school forms needed by the teachers and helps them to reduce the error in their system. Findings imply that LIS has become an integral part and plays vital role in all aspects of work of teachers and one of which is record keeping. LIS helps teachers to provide them innovative tools and resources like school forms, learner's enrollment and at the same time it aims to utilize accomplish work with minimal human intervention that reduce teachers work.

The finding is in accordance with the statements of Osakwe (2011), The purpose of record keeping for effective school management is to ensure that accurate and proper records are kept of student achievement and growth, school activities and matters that will promote school efficiency and effectiveness.

Table 4. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Extent of the Factors Affecting the Enrollment and Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Information Quality*

<i>B. Information Quality</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Learners' record in the system are complete and accurate.	3.61	Agree	5
2.	Learners' record in the system are never missing.	3.54	Agree	7
3.	Learners' record in the system are stored and can be retrieved quickly and easily.	3.57	Agree	6
4.	Learners' records are up to date. (e.g. change of residency, additional mother tongue and if CCT)	3.39	Neutral	9
5.	Learners' enrollment history are specific and precise.	3.80	Agree	4
6.	Each learner has only one unique Learner Reference Number (LRN).	3.89	Agree	3
7.	All key fields in LIS are correct and filled according to learners' information. (i.e. guardian, parents, indigenous people, mother tongue, residence, religion and special educational needs)	3.47	Neutral	8
8.	All learners' information data in the system is supported by legal documents. (i.e. live birth certificate / NSO / PSA)	3.05	Neutral	10
9.	Information output from the LIS is thorough enough. (e.g. SF1, SF2, SF3 and SF5)	3.99	Agree	1.5
10.	Information in computerize Learner Information System helps enhance management of learners' record.	3.99	Agree	1.5
Composite Mean		3.63	Agree	

As shown in the table, the factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System as perceived by the respondents with respect to information quality indicated that the respondents agree that the system includes the information output from the LIS is thorough enough. (e.g. SF1, SF2, SF3 and SF5) and computerize Learner Information System helps enhance management of learners' record. which obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.99, respectively. This means that the information quality of LIS includes the information output about the learners are in computerize form and all the details about the learners are indicated. Findings imply that LIS shows the real-time registration of learners enrolled in both public and private schools. Each learner tends to have their certain information in LIS which includes all their basic information. Moreover, they have their Learner Reference Number (LRN). It's the teacher obligation to update and secure the correct information of his / her students.

The findings are in relation with the statements of Aldarbesti and Saxena (2014) that collection of data, its conversion to the information, proper storage of information, retrieval of information and effective utilization of information need Management Information System popularly known as MIS. Management Information System is a computer-based system. It is a very strong tool available to managers for planning, organizing, executing, monitoring, control and evaluation of their operations efficiently.

Table 5. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Extent of the Factors Affecting the Enrollment and Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Availability of Learners' Data*

<i>C. Availability of Learner's Data</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>Learners presented...</i>				
1.	Certificate of Live birth.	3.63	Agree	3
2.	National Statistical Office (NSO) or Philippine Statistic Authority (PSA) certificate.	3.06	Neutral	9
3.	Baptismal certificate only.	2.87	Neutral	10
4.	updated profile. (i.e. present address, contact number, recent religion, mother tongue, ethnicity (if any) and name of guardian)	3.11	Neutral	7
5.	Basic Education Enrollment form and Affidavit of Undertakings only.	3.76	Agree	1
6.	Form 138 (Progress Report Card).	3.58	Agree	4
7.	Form 137 or SF10 - Permanent Record (for transferee).	3.46	Neutral	6
8.	Certificate of Enrollment (for transferee).	3.51	Agree	5
9.	Philippine Education Placement Test (PEPT) result (for transferee) from not accredited private schools.	3.09	Neutral	8
10.	No legal documents presented.	3.68	Agree	2
Composite Mean		3.37	Neutral	

The table shows that with regard to availability of learners' data, the respondents thought it was neutral for them which affects the enrollment and the learners' record. It indicates that respondents agrees that the system have Basic Education Enrollment form and Affidavit of Undertakings only with the highest weighted mean of 3.76. The data indicate that the extent of the factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in learner information system with respect to availability of learners' data shows that respondents agree

to each item.

Findings imply that one of the main causes of having trouble in the LIS is that the learners only undertake the form that was given to them during the enrollment. Likewise, it further shows that there are no legal documents to be presented. The needed data for the learners will be gathered using the legal documents that they will be presented. This is congruent to the literature as cited by Tangcangco (2017) that teachers thus need to respond to LIS data by intervening appropriately with learners (through informal learning counselling, adapted selection of tasks, or other guidance), subsequently using the LIS to track the effectiveness of their intervention.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Factors Affecting the Process of Enrollment of Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile

Table 6. Result of the F-test on the Significant Difference on the Perceptions on the Extent of Factors Affecting the Process of Enrollment of Learners' Record in Learner Information System as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile

Profile	F-value	P-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age				
System Quality	23.969	.000	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	11.807	.000	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	9.714	.000	Rejected	Significant
Sex				
System Quality	10.034	.002	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	10.862	.001	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	10.234	.002	Rejected	Significant
Civil Status				
System Quality	11.242	.000	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	9.871	.000	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	11.134	.000	Rejected	Significant
Position Title				
System Quality	12.754	.813	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	11.566	.968	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	9.879		Rejected	Significant
Educational Attainment				
System Quality	7.473	.000	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	3.766	.006	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	3.312	.012	Rejected	Significant
Length of Service				
System Quality	18.268	.000	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	7.532	.000	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	7.923	.000	Rejected	Significant
Seminars and Trainings Attended in LIS				
System Quality	13.768	.000	Rejected	Significant
Information Quality	8.731	.000	Rejected	Significant
Availability of Learners' Data	7.363	.000	Rejected	Significant

When grouped by age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS, all the p-values are lower than 0.05. This means that there is a reason to reject the null hypothesis. It can be inferred that the age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS of the respondents is directly contributory to their perception on the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to participation in system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data.

Findings imply that the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data wherein age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS are contributory to their perceived perception towards the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System. Findings are parallel to Senido's (2013) study about the Utilization of Information and Communication Technology in Bagong Nasyon II National High School. There is significant difference in perception of the teachers-respondents on the extent of their utilization with respect to administrative task in terms of their length of service.

Training Program to Improve the Process of Enrolling of Learners' Record in Learner Information System

Based on the findings of the research, the respondents agree that there are factors affecting the enrollment and learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data. The need for further enhancement of LIS must be done specially in the areas where their perceptions is very alarming. A literacy training on improving the process of enrolling of learners' record in Learner Information System on most recent needs in educational reform should be conducted.

A 4-day training program for offline and online Learner Information System applications will best improve the process of enrolling learner's record in LIS. This covers the up-to-date needs of the teachers that will help teachers in the process of enrolling their learners. The proposed training program answers the call in bridging the gap between teachers' skills and LIS needs of new educational reforms.

This training course is envisioned to equip the participants to enhance the skills in order to improve the process of enrolling learners' record in LIS, equip teachers with basic knowledge about the application of LIS, and efficiently use LIS for pupils' scholastic records and track.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

Based on the prescribed Most Essential Learning Competencies for English 8 in all quarters, there were 10 identified topics which were considered as most difficult and could be used in the development of enhancement materials to improve the reading skills of the students.

Evaluation for the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 was found acceptable as Learning Materials to enhance the reading skills of the students. The two groups of respondents share similar views on the Reading Enhancement Worksheets.

The developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 can be utilized as effective learning materials in teaching lessons in Research for English 8 learners.

The study concluded that the respondents' age, sex, civil status, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended in LIS are not contributory on the factors affecting the process of enrollment of learners' record in Learner Information System with respect to participation in system quality, information quality and availability of learners' data.

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